

**STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETES 2 DISEASE
(in the example of the city of Nukus in 2023)**

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Relevance of the problem: It is clear that in recent years, in our country, in accordance with the demands of the 21st century, there have been major changes in many fields, including changes in the field of medicine. In particular, equipment related to the field of endocrinology, laboratory equipment, increase in the level of knowledge as a result of training of medical personnel, patronage service in family polyclinics, rural family polyclinics, privileges created for patients with diabetes in treatment and prevention institutions, and the growth of the people's consciousness from a cultural aspect. It is observed that the incidence of diseases is increasing.

The purpose of the work: to study and statistically analyze the type 2 diabetes mellitus of citizens living in the city of Nukus in the period of 2023.

Inspection method and materials: For our investigation, 2023 archival data of the family polyclinic on the diagnosis of type 2 diabetes among citizens living in the city of Nukus were studied retrospectively.

Inspection results: At the time of inspection, it was found that there were 100 patients in total in 2021, of which 65 were male and 35 were female patients. In a retrospective review of archival data of patients, as a result of anamnesis and laboratory findings, a high rate of type 2 diabetes mellitus, ie 65%, was male patients. In the identified patients, symptoms such as dryness of the mouth, general weakness, sleep disorders, diuresis in small amounts and frequent discharges were expressed.

In the laboratory examination, it was found that the amount of sugar in the blood is on average 8.8-12.5 m/mol, and the amount of sugar in the urine is 0.5-1.5 m/mol. In 15% of male patients with diabetes mellitus, discoloration of the fingers was observed in the right big toe due to acute circulatory disorders.

Conclusion: in conclusion, it can be said that the identified patients mainly suffer from eating disorders, stressful situations in the social environment, and the patient's indifference to his health without going to the examination on time.

The reason for this was that they did not take the anti-diabetic drugs recommended by the doctors on time, and that they did not go to the medical examination every month.

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